

Legal Certainty of Farmers' Rights in the Conversion of Use of Ill Land Into Agricultural Land

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ABSTRACT

Utilization of unused land for agricultural land has an important impact on food security and community welfare. This research examines the legal certainty of farmers' rights in the context of land conversion in Indonesia. Law no. 19 of 2013 becomes a strategic framework with a focus on agricultural infrastructure, commodity prices and agricultural insurance. Farming groups have a crucial role as a forum for cooperation and production units, but agricultural land is experiencing shrinkage due to conversion. Evaluation of statutory regulations and stakeholder cooperation are needed to protect farmers' rights and ensure the sustainability of the agricultural sector. This research shows the urgency of legal clarity in land ownership, the role of village government, and protecting farmers' rights. With a focus on legal certainty and farmers' rights, this research provides in-depth insights and policy recommendations to improve legal protection and achieve sustainable development goals in the agricultural sector

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture as an economic sector has an important role in meeting food needs and community welfare. However, as time goes by, agricultural land is often converted into development for various other sectors, such as industry or housing. This land conversion can have an impact on the rights of farmers who work on the land. A farmer's group is an institution formed by farmers, breeders, or planters on the basis of shared interests, environmental conditions (social, economic, and resources), as well as closeness to improve and develop the businesses of its members. Farming groups grow and develop from, by, and for farmers who know each other, are close, trust each other, and have an interest in agricultural business, as well as similarities in traditions, settlements, and farming areas.

Agriculture plays a very important strategic role in the economy and food security. However, agricultural land has decreased due to changes in land function over time. According to data from the Ministry of Agrarian Affairs and Spatial Planning/National Land Agency, between 2013-2019, there was a reduction in rice fields of 287,000 hectares. In 2013, the national standard area of rice fields was around 7.75 million hectares, while in 2019, the national standard area of rice fields reached around 7.46 million hectares (Sitepu & Tarigan, C. 2023). This change in human function is caused by various factors, including the need for housing, development, and various other life-supporting activities. Agricultural land, which is used specifically in the agricultural sector, has experienced a decline in area according to the Central Statistics Agency. In 2018, the area of raw rice fields shrank to 7.1 million hectares, compared to 7.75 million hectares in 2017. This decrease was caused by conversion or change of land function, which changes part or all of the land from its original function to another function by negative impact on the environment and land potential (Wahyuni, 2018). The conversion of agricultural land, which includes changes in function, has a negative impact on the environment and land potential. This shift in function is often caused by economic growth and population growth which continues to increase, requiring land for daily life such as residence or business premises (Ika Janti et al, 2016).

In its development, farmer groups have three main functions, namely as a learning class, a forum for cooperation, and a production unit. As a learning class, farmer groups provide opportunities for their members to exchange information, knowledge and experiences related to agricultural practices. As a forum for cooperation, farmer groups enable the implementation of farming businesses by each member as a single business that can be developed to achieve economies of scale, both in terms of quantity, quality and continuity. According to Minister of Agriculture Regulation Number 273/Kpts/OT.160/4/2007, farmer groups are considered a vehicle for cooperation that can make a significant contribution to the development of the agricultural sector. Therefore, farming management carried out by members of farmer groups must be seen as a single business that can provide greater economic benefits through developing the business scale. Land has a vital role in people's lives, functioning as a place to live and a source of livelihood. Land use also varies depending on the party using it. For example,

farmers use it as a source of food production for survival, while the private sector invests it as capital. The government uses land for the benefit of the people. The different interests of each party can sometimes cause overlap in efforts to realize their respective interests. However, often land that was originally used for agriculture can change its function to meet other needs.

In the context of changing the function of idle land to agricultural land, there are various legal considerations that need to be taken into account. This land conversion often involves changes in land use from a utilization aspect and can result in social and economic impacts for farmers who have been working on it for a long time. Land that has not been used productively for agricultural activities can be classified as vacant land or yard. According to Albert Guttenberg (1959), land use is a key concept in urban planning, and jurisdictional authorities usually carry out land use planning to avoid conflicts. Implementing a land use plan involves land subdivision, use procedures, and regulations, such as zoning regulations.

In some cases, land in a forest that was previously used for agriculture or logging but was later left unmanaged may be considered vacant land. Usually, this land will be overgrown with non-productive plants such as shrubs. This land can be reused for agriculture, especially if farmers receive extension assistance from the government. For example, unused land or a yard that was previously unused can be converted into a tomato garden. This can be a profitable solution for farmers as market demand for tomatoes is increasing. Utilizing empty land can increase people's income, especially if farmers receive government support. Collaboration between the private sector, local government and farmers can stimulate innovation to increase the productivity of previously unused land.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Basically, farmers' rights in land use are an integral part of legal certainty that determines the rights and obligations of the parties involved. This legal certainty covers aspects such as ownership rights, cultivation rights, and protection against practices that could harm farmers. Farmers have international rights regulated in Chapter III Article 9 of Law Number 4 of 2006 which ratifies the Agreement on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. This article emphasizes that farmers have the right to store, use, exchange and sell seeds and other plant propagation materials. The importance of legal certainty regarding farmers' rights in the context of land conversion raises crucial questions such as what legal regulations regulate land conversion, to what extent farmers' rights are protected, and how legal protection efforts can be improved.

Through this research, we will explore in more depth the legal certainty of farmers' rights in the use of conversion of idle land into agricultural land. By involving literature studies, analysis of statutory regulations, and comparative legal approaches, we will try to understand the role of law in protecting farmers' rights while encouraging sustainable development. The aim of this research is to provide a clearer picture of legal certainty relating to farmers' rights in the context of land conversion, as well as provide policy recommendations that can increase legal protection for farmers and ensure the sustainability of the agricultural

sector. Thus, it is hoped that this research can make a positive contribution to our understanding of the relationship between legal certainty and farmers' rights in the use of agricultural land, as well as stimulate a broader discussion about legal protection for the agricultural sector in facing the dynamics of environmental change.

METHODOLOGY

To examine the legal certainty of farmers' rights in the use of conversion of idle land into agricultural land, several relevant research methods can be used, several research methods are applied, namely by conducting literature studies, this research will utilize literature reviews to collect relevant information and theories. relevant in relation to the legal certainty of farmers' rights in land conversion. Analysis of legal literature, statutory regulations, and case studies related to agricultural land conversion will be carried out to gain an in-depth understanding of the legal framework that regulates farmers' rights in the context of land use change.

Furthermore, this research will evaluate the laws and regulations relating to farmers' rights in the use of land conversion. An in-depth study will be conducted to analyze the extent to which these regulations provide adequate protection for farmers' rights, with a focus on clarity, certainty and fairness in their implementation. In addition, an evaluation will also be carried out on the success or failure of implementing existing legal policies, with the aim of identifying potential improvements and improvements in the protection of farmers' rights.

In the context of comparative legal analysis, this research will compare the legal systems and land conversion policies of several countries or regions. This comparison aims to evaluate the effectiveness of legal protection for farmers globally, identify best practices, and extrapolate lessons that can be applied in local legal contexts. With this approach, it is hoped that this research can contribute to an in-depth understanding of the legal certainty of farmers' rights in the use of land conversion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of the conversion of idle land into agricultural land, it is important to understand the legal certainty of the rights of the farmers involved. This is related to economic growth, food security and protecting farmers' rights. According to Ismail Ramadhan (2017:71), indicators of justice in law enforcement can be seen from how the community responds and expresses its response to the decisions handed down, because so far, justice in the context of law enforcement has depended more on the interpretation and subjective views of the law enforcers themselves. . This applies both in the context of public law enforcement, which includes general demands for justice in the relationship between society and the government, as well as in civil law enforcement, which involves private relationships between individuals and other individuals. Law enforcement, as the basis of legal supremacy, does not only expect legal obedience, but also requires law enforcement officers to implement and guarantee legal certainty based on formally applicable rules (Johan Jasin, 2019: 58).

Thus, creating a guarantee of legal certainty is an effort to protect the human rights of every Indonesian citizen. This also aims to produce a balance between rights and obligations that must be recognized and fulfilled by every member of Indonesian society, without violating the established limits. Law enforcement has the main objective of guaranteeing the realization of justice, while still paying attention to aspects of the benefits and legal certainty for society. Thus, law enforcement basically aims to realize the values of justice and truth. Therefore, the responsibility to carry out law enforcement is an obligation that must be carried out by every individual (Dahlan, 2017:221).

Law Number 4 of 2006 which ratified the Agreement on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture provides a legal basis regarding farmers' rights. Chapter III Article 9 in this law explicitly states that farmers have the right to store, use, exchange and sell seeds and plant propagation materials.

Picture 1. Utilizing Sleeping Land by Planting Vegetable Seeds

Farmers' rights in land use include the decision to convert idle land into agricultural land. Legal clarity in this case provides farmers with certainty regarding their ownership of land used for agricultural activities.

Picture 2. Land use Capacity
Source: Fanny Anugrah K, 2005

The government usually regulates land use through zoning regulations and land use ordinances. The clarity of this regulation is important to provide guidance to farmers in utilizing unused land for agricultural land, as well as avoiding land use conflicts. According to Rustiadi and Reti (2008), sustainable availability of agricultural land resources is the main requirement in achieving national food security. The availability of food agricultural land is closely related to several aspects, such as 1) potential food agricultural land resources, 2) land productivity, 3) agricultural land fragmentation, 4) scale of agricultural land control, 5) irrigation system, 6) rental or land prices agriculture, 7) land conversion, 8) farmer income, 9) human resource (HR) capacity in the agricultural sector, and 10) agricultural policy.

As a natural resource, land has a strategic role as a container and an important production factor in development activities aimed at improving human welfare. Land resources have various benefits in meeting various human needs, such as a place to live, a source of income, a tourist destination, and an agricultural area. The function of land has significance for various parties, including as a residence and livelihood for the general public. For farmers, land is a source of food production and sustainability of life. For private investors, land is considered an asset for accumulating capital. Meanwhile, for the government, land has meaning as an element of a country's sovereignty which aims for the welfare of its people.

In statutory regulations, various forms of protection have been regulated that are given to farmers' rights in response to potential abuse of power by other parties, including authorities, businessmen, or individuals with a better economic level than the party who is the victim. Examples of such protection include protection for children, labor, domestic violence, injustice and neglect. In the context of land conversion, it is important to have legal protection that ensures that farmers' rights are respected. This involves cooperation between government, communities and related parties to ensure sustainability and fairness in land use.

Law no. 19 of 2013 concerning Protection and Empowerment of Farmers, in Article 12 in conjunction with Article 7 Paragraph 2, stipulates a strategy for protecting farmers through various aspects, including:

1. Agricultural production infrastructure and facilities.
2. Business certainty.
3. Agricultural commodity prices.
4. Elimination of high cost economic practices.
5. Compensation for crop failure due to extraordinary events.
6. Early warning system and handling of climate change impacts.
7. Agricultural insurance.

In this context, the government's task is very important in providing protection to farmers, using existing facilities at the village level, such as cooperatives or soft loans from banking institutions. The active role of Village Officials and their staff is crucial to protect farmers and farm workers from potential threats that may come from investors or companies who want to invest their capital in order to make a profit. The government or village head and his

staff have a key role in protecting its citizens, especially farmers and farm workers, by carrying out selection through issuing permits. This is done so that the proposed agreement does not burden farmers and has the potential to harm them.

Positive Impact on Society and the Economy, the use of unused land for agricultural land clearly and unequivocally provides positive benefits for society and the economy. This can increase agricultural production, provide jobs, and support food security. Legal certainty regarding farmers' rights in the conversion of idle land into agricultural land is very important to create a conducive environment for sustainable agriculture. With legal clarity, farmers can carry out agricultural activities with more confidence, providing a positive impact on food security and the local economy.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, the use of unused land for agricultural land has a positive impact on society and the economy. Agriculture as an economic sector has a strategic role in meeting food needs and community welfare. In this context, legal certainty of farmers' rights is very important to provide a clear and strong basis for land use. The importance of legal certainty is emphasized by Law no. 19 of 2013 concerning the Protection and Empowerment of Farmers, which establishes strategies for protecting farmers through various aspects such as agricultural production infrastructure and facilities, business certainty, agricultural commodity prices, elimination of high-cost economic practices, compensation for crop failure, early warning systems, and agricultural insurance.

In facing changes in land function, legal clarity provides farmers with certainty regarding ownership of land used for agricultural activities. With legal protection, farmers can be more confident in carrying out agricultural activities, which in turn can increase agricultural production, provide employment opportunities and support food security. However, challenges and conflicts related to land conversion are still issues that need to be addressed. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the laws and regulations that regulate farmers' rights, and there is a need for cooperation between the government, community and related parties to ensure sustainability and fairness in land use.

Thus, this research contributes to the understanding of the relationship between legal certainty and farmers' rights in the use of agricultural land, and shows the importance of legal protection for the agricultural sector in facing the dynamics of environmental change. Implementing policies that support the protection of farmers' rights and ensure the sustainability of the agricultural sector is key to achieving sustainable development goals.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Legal Certainty of Farmers' Rights in the Conversion of Use of Ill Land Into Agricultural Land in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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